

Examining the Interplay of Knowledge, Attitudes, Practices, and Clinical Indicators in Obesity, Diabetes, and Hypertension among Overweight and Obese Individuals in Douala, Cameroon

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Abstract

Background: Global obesity has risen significantly since 1975, with a marked increase in Cameroon. This leads to metabolic syndrome (MetS) due to energy imbalance and other factors. Addressing MetS requires a comprehensive approach involving lifestyle changes and medical interventions. This study investigates the Knowledge, Attitude, and Practice (KAP) related to obesity, diabetes, and hypertension, and examines clinical parameters among overweight and obese individuals in Douala, Cameroon. **Methodology:** A cross-sectional study was conducted using structured questionnaires to gather data on KAP. Clinical parameters including

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Clinical Parameters, Comorbidities, Douala, Knowledge, Attitude, and Practice (KAP), Obesity

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glycaemia, blood pressure, and pulse rate were measured. The data was analyzed to understand the correlation between KAP and clinical parameters, and the impact of socio-demographic factors and medical history.

Results: The study found that despite having sufficient knowledge and a positive attitude, a significant number of individuals don't apply preventive or management measures for obesity, diabetes, and hypertension. Socio-demographic factors and medical history also influence these health indicators. Interestingly, over half of the participants had high blood pressure, while most had normal glycaemia and pulse rate. The study highlights the complex relationship between KAP and clinical parameters, stressing the need for comprehensive education and intervention. The findings suggest that improving KAP could indirectly help control clinical parameters.

Conclusion: This study emphasizes the role of KAP in managing obesity-related conditions. It calls for strategies that improve these aspects and regular health monitoring. The findings can guide healthcare strategies for obesity management.

Introduction

The World Health Organization notes a near tripling of global obesity since 1975. By 2016, over 1.9 billion adults were overweight, including 650 million who were obese. Overweight and obesity now cause more deaths worldwide than underweight [1]. In Cameroon, overweight and obesity rates are rising in both urban and rural areas. Also, adult obesity increased from 9.8% in 2012 to 11.4% in 2016. Similarly, the rate of overweight children under 5 rose from 6.5% in 2012 to 11% in 2019. Overweight and obesity are more prevalent among females, married individuals, and those with higher education levels [2,3].

Obesity, a result of long-term energy imbalance, leads to excess fat storage and increased BMI. The hypothalamus regulates this balance through neuro-hormonal responses controlling food intake and energy usage. Obesity is influenced by environmental and behavioral factors acting on genetic predispositions. Environmental factors encompass culture, norms, ethnicity, pollution, socioeconomic factors, and obesogenic environment. Behavioral factors include overeating, high-calorie food consumption, sedentary lifestyle, physical inactivity, diet, smoking cessation, and insufficient sleep [4,5,6]. Obesity often leads to metabolic syndrome (MetS), characterized by insulin resistance, atherogenic dyslipidemia, central obesity, and hypertension. Abdominal fat cells can elevate free fatty acid levels, disrupting blood sugar control and leading to insulin resistance, a key MetS component [7]. Globally, MetS affects up to 23.7% of adults, peaking in Australia. In 2020, it was found in 2.8% of children and 4.8% of adolescents, with the highest prevalence in the Eastern Mediterranean, Americas, and among Southern African women. In Cameroon, MetS prevalence varies. Studies found 20.6% obesity, 5.4% diabetes, 31.7% hypertension among adults, and 41.1% MetS among workers. MetS prevalence was 32.45% in Bamboutos Division and 7.0% and 17.88% among pregnant women. A Douala hospital study reported 90.3% hypertension, 79.5% obesity, and 69.8% dyslipidaemia among kidney disease patients [3,7]. So, MetS is a significant public health issue. It leads to

deteriorating health conditions in individuals and places a high financial burden on healthcare systems due to increased resource utilization, morbidity, and mortality [8]. Effective management and prevention strategies are crucial to mitigate these impacts.

Managing obesity is vital to prevent MetS and its associated conditions, underscoring the importance of a healthy lifestyle, including regular physical activity, a balanced diet, and regular medical check-ups. Obesity treatment requires a comprehensive approach, including lifestyle changes, medication, bariatric surgery, and behavior modifications. Key strategies include low-calorie, low-fat diets, increased physical activity, and lifestyle adjustments [5]. Several FDA-approved anti-obesity drugs aid weight loss and mitigate obesity-related health risks. If lifestyle changes and medications prove ineffective, bariatric surgery may be an option. Diet, exercise, and behavioral changes should be integral to all obesity management plans. The choice of treatment hinges on the individual's health status, obesity severity, and their readiness to engage in treatment [5].

The success of obesity treatment relies on an individual's readiness to participate in the intervention, which includes lifestyle changes, dietary adherence, increased physical activity, and medication compliance. This readiness is influenced by factors such as health perception, obesity severity, motivation levels, understanding of treatment benefits, and support network [9,10]. Knowledge, Attitude, and Practice (KAP) studies provide insights into individuals' understanding of obesity, attitudes towards its treatment, and behaviors related to diet, exercise, and treatment adherence [11]. Both readiness for treatment and KAP are crucial for obesity management, highlighting the need for personalized, patient-centered approaches. Clinical parameters, such as BMI and waist circumference, are key for tracking disease progression, evaluating treatment effectiveness, and predicting outcomes. Tools like continuous glucose monitoring in diabetes management and regular blood pressure readings in hypertension management are significant. For dyslipidemia, continuous evaluation of

cholesterol (total, LDL and HDL) and triglycerides is important, with changes in these levels often observed in dyslipidemias [12]. Regular follow-ups and monitoring of these parameters are essential for effective disease management and prevention of complications.

Despite its significance, there is a lack of research focusing on the KAP related to obesity and its associated conditions, such as diabetes and hypertension, among overweight and obese individuals in Cameroon. However, the necessity for a personalized, patient-focused strategy in managing obesity and its comorbidities is paramount. This approach recognizes each patient's individuality, enhances health outcomes, reduces weight stigma, and improves the quality of life. It assists patients in understanding their condition, formulating sustainable weight management plans, and eliminating treatment barriers such as weight bias [13]. Existing KAP studies regarding obesity in Cameroon, such as those conducted at the University of Yaoundé I's higher teacher's training college [14], and among the populations of Douala and Rural Manjo [6], have been limited. These studies revealed a preference for sweet tastes, unsatisfactory attitudes about obesity, and poor or moderate KAP among these populations. However, they did not evaluate the KAP on obesity comorbidities such as diabetes and hypertension. Therefore, there is a significant need for more comprehensive KAP studies on obesity in Cameroon, particularly among overweight and obese individuals. As obesity can lead to MetS, characterized by diabetes and hypertension, it is crucial to understand the KAP related to these conditions for effective health communication and intervention strategies.

This study aims to enhance health behaviors and manage obesity and its related comorbidities. It primarily explores the KAP regarding obesity among Douala's obese population, before examining the KAP associated with diabetes and hypertension. The research also determines their clinical parameters linked to these conditions. The findings will enrich discussions on obesity management and underscore the significance of KAP in health interventions.

Materials and Methods

Study Area

This study was conducted in the city of Douala, located in the Littoral Region of Cameroon. Douala, situated at an altitude of 19 m and coordinates 4°2'53''N latitude and 9°42'15''E longitude, spans an area of 210 km². As the economic capital of Cameroon and a major business hub in Central Africa, Douala is strategically positioned on both sides of the Wouri River. The city is divided into six subdivisions. As of 2015, Douala had a diverse population estimated at 4 million, growing at a rate of 6.4% [15].

Study Population and Setting

This research, conducted from November 2022 to August 2023, was a community-based cross-sectional descriptive epidemiological study. It targeted overweight and obese individuals of both genders, aged 18 and above, who had been living in Douala for at least six months. Individuals with disabilities, movement disorders, or psychiatric disorders such as were not included in the study. The study used a non-probabilistic sampling method, selecting participants based on convenience. The primary recruitment locations were Dietetic Offices in Douala. Additionally, participant recruitment campaigns were organized in major public places, including markets, major intersections, hospitals, and sports facilities, with the consent of local authorities.

To ensure a representative sample of the entire population under study, the sample size was calculated using the formula: $n = z^2pq/i^2$, where 'n' represents the sample size, 'z' stands for the Z statistic associated with a confidence level (1.96 for a 95% confidence interval), 'p' is the estimated prevalence of overweight and obesity in Cameroon, and 'i' is the margin of error (0.05). According to a study conducted by Simo et al., the considered prevalence was 31.1% [2]. Consequently, the calculated sample size was 330, increased by 15% to account for potential unsatisfactory responses or recording errors, resulting in a total of 380 individuals. Ultimately, 604 questionnaires were completed.

This research received approval from the Institutional Ethics Committee of the University of Douala (with Ethical Clearance Number 2714CEI-Udo/06/2021/M). Informed consent was duly obtained from every participant involved in the study.

Questionnaire Design and Data Collection

Trained instructors conducted the data collection. The first step was to evaluate the BMI of the participants to confirm if they were overweight or obese. This involved measuring their weight and height, and then calculating their BMI. Height was measured in a standing position without shoes using a standard strip meter with a precision of 0.5 cm, while weight was measured using a dial scale with a precision of 0.5 kg. The BMI was calculated using the formula:

$$\text{BMI (kg/m}^2\text{)} = \text{weight}/(\text{height})^2.$$

The BMI was used to categorize the participants according to WHO references [16]: overweight (25-29.99 kg/m²), and obese (≥ 30 kg/m²). Obese participants were further classified into class I (30-34.99 kg/m²), class II (35-39.99 kg/m²), and class III or morbid (≥ 40 kg/m²).

Following this, a multi-section questionnaire was filled out. This questionnaire consisted of three main parts. The first section focused on socio-demographic characteristics and medical history. The second and

third sections were centered on KAP information related to obesity and diabetes/hypertension, respectively. Socio-demographic data such as gender, age, education, and employment were collected first. Participants were also asked if they had been diagnosed with diabetes and/or hypertension.

The study utilized a questionnaire to collect data on KAP about obesity. This questionnaire, outlined in Box 1, consisted of 42 questions: 14 related to knowledge, 15 to attitude, and 13 to practices. The questionnaire's design was based on a model proposed by Reethesh et al. [17], who developed and validated a similar tool for assessing KAP about obesity among overweight and obese individuals. For the assessment of KAP about diabetes and hypertension, a separate questionnaire was used (Box 2). This questionnaire contained 33 items: 16 questions related to knowledge, 9 to attitude, and 8 to practices. The design of this questionnaire was based on previous studies conducted on KAP about diabetes and/or hypertension, specifically those by Kurian et al. [18], Tahir et al. [19], Buang et al. [20], and Sitaula et al. [21]. These questionnaires were instrumental in gathering comprehensive data for the study.

The second crucial aspect of this study involved assessing the clinical parameters related to obesity, diabetes, and hypertension among the participants. Therefore, during the study's final phase, measurements were taken for participants' glycaemia, pulse rate, and blood pressure. The OneTouch Select Plus Simple® GL-SPS-2000017 model, an automatic Blood Glucose Meter (LifeScan IP Holdings, USA), was used to determine fasting glycaemia. Pulse rate, systolic and diastolic blood pressure were measured using the Paramed B22S, an automated sphygmomanometer (PARAMED, Canada). (For these latter, three successive measurements were taken from the participant's non-dominant arm while seated, with a five-minute gap between each. The mean of these three readings was used for clinical pulse and blood pressure analysis, ensuring data accuracy and reliability.

Participants were divided into three groups based on their blood glucose levels, as previously outlined by Barennes et al. [22]: low glycaemia (under 0.6g/L), normal glycaemia (between 0.6 g/L and 1.10 g/L), and high glycaemia (over 1.10 g/L). Similarly, participants were grouped based on their pulse rate, systolic blood pressure, and diastolic blood pressure, as per Coll-de-Tuero et al. [23]. Pulse rates under 60 beats per minute (bpm) were considered low, between 60 and 100 bpm as normal, and over 100 bpm as high. Systolic blood

pressure was deemed low if under 90 mmHg, normal between 90 and 130 mmHg, and high if over 130 mmHg. Diastolic blood pressure followed a similar pattern: low for values under 60 mmHg, normal between 60 and 90 mmHg, and high over 90 mmHg.

Data Handling and Statistical Analysis

Data was meticulously organized into an MS Excel spreadsheet for in-depth statistical analysis. In the KAP study, each question was evaluated and assigned a score based on the responses. These scores were then cumulatively added for each KAP component. Box 1 presents the scoring key for KAP in relation to obesity, as proposed by Reethesh et al. [17]. The total score for the knowledge component varied from 14 to 70, with 14-28 indicating very poor knowledge, 28-42 poor, 42-56 good, and 56-70 excellent. The attitude component had a total score range of 15 to 75, with 15-45 reflecting a negative attitude and 45-75 a positive one. The practice component concerning obesity had a total score range of 13 to 65, with 13-26 deemed very poor, 26 - 39 poor, 39 - 52 good, and 52 - 65 excellent. Box 2 illustrates the scoring key for KAP regarding diabetes and obesity. Similar to the previous component, the scores corresponding to the participants' responses were cumulatively added. The total score for the knowledge component varied from 16 to 48, with 16-24 indicating very poor knowledge, 24-32 poor, 32-40 good, 40-48 excellent. The attitude component had a total score range of 9 to 27, with 9-18 indicating a negative attitude and 18-27 a positive one. The practice component concerning obesity had a total score range of 8 to 13.5, with 8-13.5 considered very poor, 13.5-19 poor, 19-24.5 good, and 24.5-30 excellent. In terms of clinical parameters, including glycaemia, pulse rate, systolic and diastolic pressure, and each participant's values were classified as low, normal, or high based on the cut-off values provided in the previous section.

The data were analyzed in two stages. Initially, they were processed based on the respondents' weight status. Subsequently, they were treated according to socio-demographic parameters (such as gender, age, education, and employment) and medical history (including diabetes and hypertension). Frequency and relative frequency were computed using SPSS 20 (IBM Corp.). Correlations were determined between KAP components, between clinical parameters, and between KAP components and clinical parameters. Inferential statistical tests, including the χ^2 test and Pearson correlation coefficient, were utilized. A p-value less than 0.05 was deemed statistically significant.

Box 1

QUESTIONNAIRE
Knowledge
<p>1. <i>Obesity can be assessed by an entity called BMI:</i> a. Definitely b. Probably c. Probably not d. Definitely not e. Don't know</p> <p>2. <i>More fat over abdomen is dangerous than overall increase in the distribution of fat in terms of causing increased cardiovascular problems:</i> a. Definitely b. Probably c. Probably not d. Definitely not e. Don't know</p> <p>3. <i>Obesity is associated with heart diseases, such as heart attack, increased blood pressure, increased cholesterol levels, etc.</i> a. Definitely b. Probably c. Probably not d. Definitely not e. Don't know</p> <p>4. <i>Obesity is associated with diabetes:</i> a. Definitely b. Probably c. Probably not d. Definitely not e. Don't know</p> <p>5. <i>Obesity is associated with osteoarthritis (joint problems):</i> a. Definitely b. Probably c. Probably not d. Definitely not e. Don't know</p> <p>6. <i>Fasting/skipping meals is a good way to lose weight:</i> a. Definitely b. Probably c. Probably not d. Definitely not e. Don't know</p> <p>7. <i>Excess sugar consumption in the form of sweets; additional sugars in coffee/tea/milk etc., is an important risk factor which leads to overweight/obesity:</i> a. Definitely b. Probably c. Probably not d. Definitely not e. Don't know</p> <p>8. <i>Frequent consumption of sugar-sweetened beverages (pepsi/coca-cola/sweetened juices, etc.) leads to weight gain:</i> a. Definitely b. Probably c. Probably not d. Definitely not e. Don't know</p> <p>9. <i>Frequent fried food consumption (samosa, fries, wafers, etc.) leads to weight gain:</i> a. Definitely b. Probably c. Probably not d. Definitely not e. Don't know</p> <p>10. <i>Excessive consumption of refined foods (bread/biscuits/momos, etc.) leads to weight gain:</i> a. Definitely b. Probably c. Probably not d. Definitely not e. Don't know</p> <p>11. <i>Constant stress is a risk factor which leads to weight gain:</i> a. Definitely b. Probably c. Probably not d. Definitely not e. Don't know</p> <p>12. <i>Regular aerobic exercises, such as running, jogging, swimming, playing outdoor sports, etc., is an important way of losing weight:</i> a. Definitely b. Probably c. Probably not d. Definitely not e. Don't know</p> <p>13. <i>Anti-obesity drugs are the preferred way of reducing weight:</i> a. Definitely b. Probably c. Probably not d. Definitely not e. Don't know</p> <p>14. <i>Meal replacers/supplements are a healthy way to lose weight:</i> a. Definitely b. Probably c. Probably not d. Definitely not e. Don't know</p>
Attitude
<p>15. <i>I consider myself obese:</i> a. Definitely b. Probably c. Probably not d. Definitely not e. Don't know</p> <p>16. <i>I consider my current weight to be harmful for my health:</i> a. Definitely b. Probably c. Probably not d. Definitely not e. Don't know</p> <p>17. <i>I am motivated to lose weight:</i> a. Always b. Very often c. Sometimes d. Rarely e. Never</p> <p>18. <i>I find it difficult to keep my weight steady:</i> a. Always b. Very often c. Sometimes d. Rarely e. Never</p> <p>19. <i>I consider regular breakfast intake to be a part of healthy lifestyle:</i> a. Definitely b. Probably c. Probably not d. Definitely not e. Don't know</p> <p>20. <i>I consider small and frequent meals help in weight reduction:</i> a. Definitely b. Probably c. Probably not d. Definitely not e. Don't know</p> <p>21. <i>I am confident that I would reduce sugars/sweets in my diet:</i> a. Extremely confident b. Very confident c. Moderately confident d. Slightly confident e. Not at all confident</p> <p>22. <i>I am confident that I would avoid fried foods:</i> a. Extremely confident b. Very confident c. Moderately confident d. Slightly confident e. Not at all confident</p> <p>23. <i>I am confident that I would prefer salads/low calorie snacks instead of sweets/fried foods/refined foods in my diet:</i> a. Extremely confident b. Very confident c. Moderately confident d. Slightly confident e. Not at all confident</p> <p>24. <i>I am satisfied of my current physical activity level:</i> a. Very satisfied b. Satisfied c. Neither d. Dissatisfied e. Very dissatisfied</p> <p>25. <i>I am confident that I would do physical activities such as jogging, bicycling, swimming, competitive sports, or any other activity that makes me healthy:</i> a. Extremely confident b. Very confident c. Moderately confident d. Slightly confident e. Not at all confident</p> <p>26. <i>I am confident that I would engage in some sort of household activities when I am free:</i> a. Extremely confident b. Very confident c. Moderately confident d. Slightly confident e. Not at all confident</p> <p>27. <i>I am confident that I would use stairs instead of lift:</i> a. Extremely confident b. Very confident c. Moderately confident d. Slightly confident e. Not at all confident</p>

<p>28. I am confident that I would go to nearby places by walk: a. Extremely confident b. Very confident c. Moderately confident d. Slightly confident e. Not at all confident</p> <p>29. I feel sad/depressed considering that I am obese/overweight: a. Always b. Very often c. Sometimes d. Rarely e. Never</p>
<p>Practice</p> <p>30. I add additional sugars in my coffee/tea/buttermilk: a. Always b. Very often c. Sometimes d. Rarely e. Never</p> <p>31. I take sweet dish after meals: a. Always b. Very often c. Sometimes d. Rarely e. Never</p> <p>32. I use helpers for my household activities: a. Always b. Very often c. Sometimes d. Rarely e. Never</p> <p>33. I eat in response to stress: a. All the time b. Most often c. Some of the time d. Seldom e. Never</p> <p>34. I drink sugar sweetened beverages: a. Never b. Rarely c. 1-2/week d. 2-3/week e. >3/week</p> <p>35. I consume fried foods: a. Never b. Rarely c. 1-2/week d. 2-3/week e. >3/week</p> <p>36. How often do you take three major meals and two minor meals in a week? a. All 7 days a week b. 5-6 times a week c. 3-4 times a week d. Once a week e. Never</p> <p>37. Apart from the three major meals and two minor meals, how many snacks do you usually consume in a day? a. 0 b. 1 c. 2 d. 3 e. More than 3</p> <p>38. I include fruits/salads in my diet: a. More than once a day b. 4-6 times a week c. 1-3 times a week d. Once in 15 days e. Never</p> <p>39. How frequently do you exercise? a. Everyday b. 4-6 times/week c. 1-3 times/week d. Once a month e. Never</p> <p>40. For how long do you exercise in a day? a. Not at all b. 60 mins c. 15-30 mins d. 30-60 mins e. >60 mins</p> <p>41. I consult my doctor/dietitian for weight reduction: a. Always b. Very often c. Sometimes d. Rarely e. Never</p> <p>42. Which of the following statements best applies to you? a. I currently exercise regularly and have done so for more than 6 months b. In the last 6 months I have started exercising regularly c. I currently exercise but not regularly d. I currently do not exercise and intend to start regular exercise in the next 6 months e. I currently do not exercise and do not intend to start regular exercise in next 6 months</p>
<p>SCORE KEY</p> <p>For questions 6, 13, 14, 18, 24, 29, 30, 31, 33, 40: a=1, b=2, c=3, d=4, e=5</p> <p>For questions 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 15, 16, 17, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 25, 26, 27, 28, 32, 34, 35, 36, 37, 38, 39, 41, 42: a=5, b=4, c=3, d=2, e=1</p>

Box 2

<p>QUESTIONNAIRE</p>
<p>Knowledge</p> <p>1. Have you ever heard of diabetes? a. Yes b. No c. I don't know</p> <p>2. Do you know the symptoms of diabetes? a. Yes b. No c. I don't know</p> <p>3. Do you know what a glucose tolerance test is? a. Yes b. No c. I don't know</p> <p>4. Do you know how to diagnose diabetes? a. Yes b. No c. I don't know</p> <p>5. Do you know that diabetes can be a genetic/hereditary disease? a. Yes b. No c. I don't know</p> <p>6. Are you aware of the complications of diabetes (eye disease, foot ulcer, kidney disease, heart problems, hypertension...)? a. Yes b. No c. I don't know</p> <p>7. Have you ever heard of hypertension? a. Yes b. No c. I don't know</p> <p>8. Do you know the symptoms of hypertension? a. Yes b. No c. I don't know</p> <p>9. Do you know how to diagnose hypertension? a. Yes b. No c. I don't know</p> <p>10. Do you know that salt consumption is a risk factor for hypertension? a. Yes b. No c. I don't know</p> <p>11. Do you know the complications of hypertension (eye disease, kidney disease, heart problems, stroke...)? a. Yes b. No c. I don't know</p> <p>12. Do you know that smoking is a risk factor for diabetes and hypertension? a. Yes b. No c. I don't know</p> <p>13. Do you know that alcohol is a risk factor for diabetes and hypertension? a. Yes b. No c. I don't know</p> <p>14. Do you know that obesity is a risk factor for diabetes and hypertension? a. Yes b. No c. I don't know</p> <p>15. Do you know that exercise/physical activity can be useful in preventing and managing diabetes and hypertension? a. Yes b. No c. I don't know</p> <p>16. Do you know that healthy eating habits (meal times and eating style, reduction in salt, sugar, and fats/oils intake) can be useful in preventing and managing diabetes and hypertension? a. Yes b. No c. I don't know</p>
<p>Attitude</p>

<p>17. <i>Diabetes is a lifelong disease:</i> a. I agree b. So-so c. I disagree</p> <p>18. <i>Regular blood sugar check is important:</i> a. I agree b. So-so c. I disagree</p> <p>19. <i>Hypertension is a lifelong disease:</i> a. I agree b. So-so c. I do not agree</p> <p>20. <i>Regular monitoring of blood pressure is important:</i> a. I agree b. So-so c. I disagree</p> <p>21. <i>A healthy diet is important for the prevention and control of diabetes and hypertension:</i> a. I agree b. So-so c. I disagree</p> <p>22. <i>We can stop taking medicines after controlling diabetes and hypertension:</i> a. I agree b. So-so c. I disagree</p> <p>23. <i>Long-term use of medications for diabetes and hypertension is harmful:</i> a. I agree b. So-so c. I disagree</p> <p>24. <i>It is important to observe compliance with hypertension medications (take medications on time and as prescribed by the doctor):</i> a. I agree b. So-so c. I disagree</p> <p>25. <i>Traditional herbs can provide reliable alternatives to standard medicines:</i> a. I agree b. So-so c. I disagree</p>
<p>Practices</p> <p>26. <i>How often do you check your blood sugar?</i> a. Never b. Every day c. Every week d. Every month</p> <p>27. <i>How often do you check your blood pressure?</i> a. Never b. Every day c. Every week d. Every month</p> <p>28. <i>Do you visit diabetes education/awareness centers?</i> a. Yes b. No</p> <p>29. <i>Do you usually add extra sugar to your diet?</i> a. Yes b. No</p> <p>30. <i>Do you visit hypertension education/awareness centers?</i> a. Yes b. No</p> <p>31. <i>Do you usually add extra salt to your diet?</i> a. Yes b. No</p> <p>32. <i>Do you consume alcohol?</i> a. Yes b. No</p> <p>33. <i>Do you smoke or are you exposed to passive smoking?</i> a. Yes b. No</p>
<p>SCORE KEY</p> <p>- For questions with four options Question 26, 27: a=1, b=2, c=3, d=4</p> <p>- For questions with three options Questions 17, 19: a=1, b=2, c=3</p> <p>Questions 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 18, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25: a=3, b=2, c=1</p> <p>- For questions with two options Questions 29, 31, 32, 33: a=1, b=2</p> <p>Questions 28, 30: a=2, b=1</p>

Results

Out of the 604 questionnaires that were initially filled out, 61 were excluded due to incomplete or inconsistent information. Consequently, the final analysis was conducted on the remaining 543 questionnaires. The average baseline measurements for the participants in the study were as follows: BMI: 32.28±6.34 kg/m², glycaemia: 0.99±0.22 g/L, pulse rate: 73.08±10.67 bpm, systolic blood pressure: 132.74±14.00 mmHg, and diastolic blood pressure: 81.44±11.69 mmHg.

The analysis further revealed that 205 participants, representing 37.8% of the sample, were overweight, while 338 (62.2%) participants were classified as obese. The obese participants were further divided into three classes: 200 participants (36.8%) with class I obesity, 61 participants (11.2%) with class II obesity, and 77 participants (14.2%) with class III obesity. This data provides a comprehensive overview of the prevalence of overweight and obesity among the study participants.

Socio-demographic characteristics and medical history of obese individual from Douala

Table 1 provides a detailed breakdown of the participants' socio-demographic parameters and medical history, categorized by their weight status. Out

of the participants, 244 (44.9%) were males and 299 (55.1%) were females. The majority (58.2%) of the male participants were overweight, while most of the female participants fell into the class I obesity category (51.5%). The average age of the participants was 44.63±14.37 years. A significant portion of the participants (50.6%) were aged between 30 to 50 years. Participants up to 60 years old were primarily overweight or class I obese, while those over 60 years old were predominantly obese. In terms of education, most participants had attended either secondary school (49.5%) or university (47.2%). All the 18 participants who had only primary education were class II obese. Those who attended secondary school were mostly class I obese (44.6%), and those who attended university were mostly overweight (59.4%). Regarding employment status, the majority of the participants were workers (61.0%). Both workers and non-workers were mainly overweight, while retirees were predominantly class II and class III obese.

As for medical history, 78 participants (14.4%) reported having been diagnosed with diabetes, and 159 participants (29.3%) reported having been diagnosed with hypertension. Participants with diabetes were mainly class I (42.3%) and class III obese (46.2%), while

those without diabetes were primarily overweight (43.0%) and class I obese (35.9%). Similarly, participants with hypertension were mainly class I obese (40.3%),

while those without hypertension were primarily overweight (44.5%).

Table 1: Socio-Demographic Features and Medical History of Overweight and Obese Individuals in Douala, Categorized by Weight Status

	Total (n = 543)	Weight status				P
		Overweight	Obese class I	Obese class II	Obese class III	
SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC PARAMETERS						
Gender						
Male (n = 244)	244 (44.9%)	142 (58.2%)	46 (18.9%)	23 (9.4%)	33 (13.5%)	<0.0001
Female (n = 299)	299 (55.1%)	63 (21.1%)	154 (51.5%)	40 (12.7%)	44 (14.7%)	
Age						
<30 (n = 85)	85 (15.7%)	37 (43.6%)	24 (28.2%)	0 (0.0%)	24 (28.2%)	<0.0001
[30-40[(n = 163)	163 (30.0%)	108 (66.3%)	55 (33.7%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	
[40-50[(n = 128)	128 (23.6%)	16 (12.5%)	75 (58.6%)	28 (21.9%)	9 (7.0%)	
[50-60[(n = 63)	63 (11.6%)	34 (54.0%)	13 (20.6%)	9 (14.3%)	7 (11.1%)	
≥60 (n = 104)	104 (19.1%)	10 (9.6%)	33 (31.7%)	24 (23.1%)	37 (35.6%)	
Education						
Primary studies (n = 18)	18 (3.3%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	18 (100.0%)	0 (0.0%)	<0.0001
Secondary studies (n = 269)	269 (49.5%)	53 (19.7%)	120 (44.6%)	43 (16.0%)	53 (19.7%)	
University studies (n = 256)	256 (47.2%)	152 (59.4%)	80 (31.3%)	0 (0.0%)	24 (9.4%)	
Employment						
Working (n = 331)	331 (61.0%)	139 (42.0%)	139 (42.0%)	37 (11.2%)	16 (4.8%)	<0.0001
Not working (n = 141)	141 (26.0%)	60 (39.7%)	55 (39.0%)	0 (0.0%)	30 (21.3%)	
Retirement (n = 71)	71 (13.0%)	10 (14.1%)	6 (8.5%)	24 (33.8%)	31 (43.7%)	
MEDICAL HISTORY						
Diabetes						
Yes (n = 78)	78 (14.4%)	5 (6.4%)	33 (42.3%)	4 (5.1%)	36 (46.2%)	<0.0001
No (n = 465)	465 (85.6%)	200 (43.0%)	167 (35.9%)	57 (12.3%)	41 (8.8%)	
Hypertension						
Yes (n = 159)	159 (29.3%)	34 (21.4%)	64 (40.3%)	28 (17.6%)	33 (20.8%)	<0.0001
No (n = 384)	384 (70.7%)	171 (44.5%)	136 (35.4%)	33 (8.6%)	44 (11.5%)	

Overweight: BMI 25-29.99 kg/m²; **Obese class I:** BMI 30-34.99 kg/m²; **Obese class II:** BMI 35-39.99 kg/m²; **Obese class III or morbid:** BMI ≥40 kg/m²

KAP of Obese Individual from Douala Regarding Obesity, Diabetes, and Hypertension

KAP of participants according to weight status

Table 2 firstly presents the KAP of participants regarding obesity, and secondly their KAP regarding diabetes, and hypertension. The responders had excellent and good knowledge regarding obesity (99.1%), with no people having very poor knowledge and only 5 (0.9%) responders having poor knowledge. Moreover, almost all participants (94.7%) had a positive attitude regarding obesity, with only 5.3% having a negative attitude. However, a considerable proportion of responders had poor and very poor practices (17.9%), with 446 (82.1%) having good and excellent

practices. These trends for KAP about obesity were the same regardless of the weight status of participants, with only some exceptions.

Concerning KAP about diabetes and hypertension, the trends are slightly different from those noted above for KAP about obesity. In fact, a considerable number of responders had poor knowledge (7.9%) and negative attitude (7.9%). Even more, almost all participants had poor and very poor practices (99.1%), with only 5 (0.9%) participants having good practices. As noted above for KAP about obesity, the trends of KAP about diabetes and hypertension seem to not be affected by weight status.

Table 2: KAP Concerning Obesity, Diabetes, and Hypertension among Overweight and Obese Individuals in Douala, Categorized by Weight Status

	Total (n = 543)	Weight status				P
		Overweight (n = 205)	Obese class I (n = 200)	Obese class II (n = 61)	Obese class III (n = 77)	
OBESITY						
Knowledge						
Poor	5 (0.9%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	5 (6.5%)	<0.0001
Good	135 (24.8%)	57 (27.8%)	48 (24.0%)	17 (27.9%)	12 (15.6%)	
Excellent	403 (74.3%)	148 (72.2%)	152 (76.0%)	44 (72.1%)	60 (77.9%)	
Attitude						
Negative	29 (5.3%)	10 (4.9%)	10 (5.0%)	8 (13.1%)	1 (1.3%)	0.0193
Positive	514 (94.7%)	195 (95.1%)	190 (95.0%)	53 (86.9%)	76 (98.7%)	
Practices						
Very poor	8 (1.5%)	3 (1.5%)	4 (2.0%)	1 (1.6%)	0 (0.0%)	<0.0001
Poor	89 (16.4%)	31 (15.1%)	32 (16.0%)	19 (31.1%)	7 (9.1%)	
Good	208 (38.3%)	87 (42.4%)	47 (43.5%)	25 (41.0%)	9 (11.7%)	
Excellent	238 (43.8%)	84 (41.0%)	77 (38.5%)	16 (26.3%)	61 (79.2%)	
DIABETES AND HYPERTENSION						
Knowledge						
Poor	40 (7.4%)	15 (7.3%)	18 (9.0%)	1 (1.6%)	6 (7.8%)	<0.0001
Good	105 (19.3%)	28 (13.7%)	26 (13.0%)	13 (21.3%)	38 (49.3%)	
Excellent	398 (73.3%)	162 (79.0%)	156 (78.0%)	47 (77.1%)	33 (42.9%)	
Attitude						
Negative	43 (7.9%)	12 (5.9%)	20 (10.0%)	5 (8.2%)	6 (7.8%)	<0.0001
Positive	500 (92.1%)	193 (94.1%)	180 (90.0%)	56 (91.8%)	71 (92.2%)	
Practices						
Very poor	79 (14.5%)	33 (16.1%)	25 (12.5%)	17 (27.9%)	9 (11.7%)	0.0069
Poor	454 (83.6%)	172 (83.9%)	170 (85.0%)	44 (72.1%)	68 (88.3%)	
Good	5 (0.9%)	0 (0.0%)	5 (2.5%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	

Overweight: BMI 25-29.99 kg/m²; **Obese class I:** BMI 30-34.99 kg/m²; **Obese class II:** BMI 35-39.99 kg/m²; **Obese class III or morbid:** BMI ≥40 kg/m²

Correlation between KAP components among overweight and obese individuals from Douala

Correlation between knowledge, attitude, and practices of responders regarding obesity, and regarding diabetes and hypertension has been done and is presented in Table 3. One notes for KAP about obesity, a significant positive correlation is noted between the three parameters. However, for KAP about diabetes and hypertension, a significant positive correlation is noted between knowledge and attitude, attitude and practice, while between knowledge and practices, a significant negative correlation is noted. Regarding the correlation between KAP about obesity

and KAP about diabetes and hypertension, a significant positive correlation is noted between knowledge on obesity and knowledge on diabetes/hypertension, between knowledge on obesity and attitude on diabetes/hypertension, between practice on obesity and knowledge of diabetes/hypertension, and between attitude on obesity and practice of diabetes/hypertension. However, a significant negative correlation is noted between knowledge on obesity and practices of diabetes/hypertension, between attitude on obesity and knowledge on diabetes/hypertension, and between attitude on obesity and knowledge on diabetes/hypertension.

Table 3: Correlation between KAP Concerning Obesity, Diabetes and Hypertension among Overweight and Obese Individuals in Douala

		Obesity			Diabetes/hypertension		
		Knowledge	Attitude	Practices	Knowledge	Attitude	Practices
Obesity	Knowledge	1					
	Attitude	+0,46***	1				
	Practices	+0,29***	+0,15**	1			
Diabetes hypertension	Knowledge	+0,33***	-0,18***	+0,27***	1		
	Attitude	+0,16**	-0,11*	+0,07 ^{ns}	+0,23***	1	
	Practices	-0,15**	+0,20***	+0,06 ^{ns}	-0,44***	+0,10*	1

Note: ns: no significant correlation at P < 0.05; *: significant correlation at P < 0.05; **: significant correlation at P < 0.01; ***: significant correlation at P < 0.001

KAP among overweight and obese individuals from Douala according to socio-demographic parameters and medical history

KAP of responders have been analyzed according to socio-demographic parameters and medical history and are shown in Table 4 (Appendix). We note regarding the impact of socio-demographic parameters, that female responders had better KAP about obesity compared to males. For KAP regarding diabetes and hypertension, male responders had better knowledge and attitude, while females had better practices. KAP regarding obesity presented the same trends regardless of the age of responders. However, participants less than 30 years old had weaker attitudes compared to those older. Participants aged between 30 and 50 years old had better knowledge and practices compared to those younger or older. Regarding the impact of responders' age on KAP about diabetes and hypertension, the trends of attitude and practices did not vary with age, while knowledge seemed to increase with age. Regarding the impact of education, participants who attended secondary school and university had better KAP regarding obesity and diabetes/hypertension compared to those who only attended primary school. Employment status did not significantly influence the trends of KAP regarding both obesity and diabetes/hypertension, except for practices about obesity. Participants who were working had better practices regarding obesity compared to those not working or retirees.

Regarding the effect of medical history, participants without diabetes had better knowledge and practices regarding obesity compared to those with diabetes, with both groups having the same attitude. For KAP regarding diabetes and hypertension, participants without diabetes had weaker knowledge compared to those with diabetes. The trends of attitude and practices were the same for both groups. Regarding the impact of hypertension, responders without hypertension had better KAP regarding obesity

compared to those with hypertension. However, those with hypertension had better knowledge regarding diabetes and hypertension, while the trends of attitude and practices about diabetes and hypertension were the same for those with or without hypertension.

Clinical Parameters of Overweight and Obese Individuals from Douala

Clinical parameters of overweight and obese individuals from Douala according to their weight status

Table 5 provides a breakdown of obesity levels in Douala, categorized by glycaemia, pulse rate, and blood pressure. It's noteworthy that out of all respondents, 97.4% (529 individuals) exhibited normal glycaemia, while a mere 2.6% (14 individuals) showed high glycaemia. Respondents with Class II and III obesity tended to display higher glycaemia compared to those who were overweight or Class I obese. In terms of pulse rate, the vast majority of participants (94.3%) fell within the normal range, with only 5.7% exhibiting a high pulse rate. Interestingly, overweight individuals appeared to have a higher pulse rate compared to their obese counterparts. When it comes to blood pressure, the data diverges from the trends observed in glycaemia and pulse rate. Over half of the respondents (59.3%) had high systolic pressure, with overweight individuals less likely to experience high systolic pressure compared to those who were obese. Diastolic pressure was also elevated in a significant number of respondents, albeit not as frequently as systolic pressure. Specifically, 30.8% of respondents had high diastolic pressure, while 69.2% had normal levels. Similar to systolic pressure, obese respondents were more likely to have high diastolic pressure compared to those who were overweight. Overall, it's important to note that none of the respondents exhibited low values for any of the four parameters under consideration.

Table 5: Clinical Parameters of Overweight and Obese Individuals from Douala, Based on Weight Status

	Total (n = 543)	Weight status				P
		Overweight (n = 205)	Obese class I (n = 200)	Obese class II (n = 61)	Obese class III (n = 77)	
Glycaemia						
Normal (0.60-1.10 g/L)	529 (97.4%)	200 (97.6%)	200 (100%)	57 (93.4%)	72 (93.5%)	0.0031
High (>1.10 g/L)	14 (2.6%)	5 (2.4%)	0 (0.0%)	4 (6.6%)	5 (6.5%)	
Pulse rate						
Normal (60-100 bpm)	512 (94.3%)	178 (86.8%)	200 (100%)	57 (93.4%)	77 (100.0%)	<0.0001
High (>100 bpm)	31 (5.7%)	27 (13.2%)	0 (0.0%)	4 (6.6%)	0 (0.0%)	
Blood pressure						
Systolic						
Normal (90-130 mmHg)	221 (40.7%)	147 (71.7%)	28 (14.0%)	33 (54.1%)	13 (16.9%)	<0.0001
High (>130 mmHg)	322 (59.3%)	58 (28.3%)	172 (86.0%)	28 (45.9%)	64 (83.1%)	

Diastolic						
Normal (60-90 mmHg)	376 (69.2%)	164 (80.0%)	134 (65.5%)	37 (60.7%)	44 (57.1%)	0.0002
High (>90 mmHg)	167 (30.8%)	41 (20.0%)	71 (34.5%)	24 (39.3%)	33 (42.9%)	

Correlation between clinical parameters of overweight and obese individuals from Douala

Table 6 presents the correlation between BMI, pulse rate, and both systolic and diastolic pressure. It's observed that glycaemia, pulse rate, and both systolic

and diastolic pressure have a significant positive correlation with BMI. Furthermore, these four parameters also show a significant positive correlation with each other.

Table 6: Correlation between Clinical Parameters of Overweight and Obese Individuals from Douala

	BMI	Glycaemia	Pulse Rate	Blood pressure	
				Systolic	Diastolic
BMI	1				
Glycaemia	+0.30***	1			
Pulse rate	+0.11**	+0.21***	1		
Systolic blood pressure	+0.53***	+0.28***	+0.19***	1	
Diastolic blood pressure	+0.50***	+0.19***	+0.35***	+0.88***	1

Note: BMI: Body mass index; **: significant correlation at P< 0.01; ***: significant correlation at P< 0.001

Correlation between KAP and Clinical Parameters of Overweight and Obese Individuals from Douala

Table 7 illustrates the relationship between KAP components and various clinical parameters in overweight and obese individuals from Douala. It's observed that knowledge about obesity is positively associated with BMI, pulse rate, and both systolic and diastolic pressure. However, there is a non-significant negative correlation between this knowledge and blood glucose levels. Attitude, on the other hand, shows a negative correlation with blood glucose levels

and pulse rate, but a positive correlation with other clinical parameters. Practices are positively associated with all clinical parameters. When it comes to KAP about diabetes and hypertension, knowledge shows a positive correlation with all clinical parameters under study. Attitude, however, is negatively associated with all clinical parameters, except for pulse rate. Practices show a negative correlation with pulse rate, systolic and diastolic pressure, but a positive correlation with BMI and blood glucose levels.

Table 7: Correlation between KAP Components and Clinical parameters of Overweight and Obese Individuals in Douala

			CLINICAL PARAMETERS				
			BMI	Glycaemia	Pulse rate	Blood pressure	
						Systolic	Diastolic
KAP COMPONENTS	Obesity	Knowledge	+0.21***	-0.03 ^{ns}	+0.02 ^{ns}	+0.23***	+0.28***
		Attitude	+0.07 ^{ns}	-0.07 ^{ns}	-0.15***	+0.10*	+0.09*
		Practices	+0.18***	+0.18***	+0.03 ^{ns}	+0.21***	+0.19***
	Diabetes / hypertension	Knowledge	+0.12**	+0.12**	+0.11*	+0.14**	+0.15***
		Attitude	-0.09*	-0.11*	+0.03 ^{ns}	-0.13*	-0.05 ^{ns}
		Practices	+0.08 ^{ns}	+0.18***	-0.03 ^{ns}	-0.01 ^{ns}	-0.01 ^{ns}

Note: BMI: Body mass index; KAP: Knowledge, attitude, and practices; ns: no significant correlation at P < 0.05; *: significant correlation at P< 0.05; **: significant correlation at P< 0.01; ***: significant correlation at P< 0.001

Discussion

This study investigates the KAP related to obesity, diabetes, and hypertension among overweight and obese individuals in Douala, involving 543 participants, mainly women over 30 with secondary or university education (Table 1). It confirms that obesity risk is higher among women, educated individuals, and workers due to factors like decreased physical activity and diet changes [2,6,24,25]. The study reveals a higher

prevalence of hypertension than diabetes in this group, supported by participants' average blood glucose levels (0.99±0.22 g/L) and systolic pressure (132.74±14.00 mmHg). The correlation between BMI and these health parameters (Table 6) indicates that obesity severity increases the occurrence of these conditions. The KAP study reveals that 99.1% of obese individuals in Douala are well-informed about obesity (Table 2), a contrast to the general population's limited knowledge

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[6]. This indicates that people often seek information post becoming obese. Despite the crucial role of this knowledge in obesity prevention, it is often sought after becoming obese. The study also found obese individuals to be more knowledgeable than the overweight (Table 2), with no correlation between BMI and knowledge (Table 7). This underscores the need for obesity education among the general population, especially non-obese individuals, to promote preventive behaviors [26]. Our study also shows that 94.7% of obese respondents in Douala have a positive attitude towards obesity, contrasting with the general population's moderate attitude [6]. This suggests that overweight and obese individuals, motivated to lose weight, tend to seek information post becoming obese. A positive correlation was found between BMI and attitude (Table 7), and attitude was linked to knowledge (Table 3). These findings highlight the need to improve the general population's attitude towards obesity, particularly among non-obese individuals. A positive attitude enhances self-efficacy, increases motivation for healthy behaviors, and helps individuals overcome setbacks in their weight loss journey. Healthcare providers with a positive attitude adhere more to obesity treatment guidelines, provide better care, and can serve as role models for their patients [27,28]. A positive attitude can also reduce weight-related stigma, which can negatively impact mental health and hinder weight loss efforts. Our study on obesity practices in Douala reveals that while 82.1% of participants exhibit good or excellent practices (Table 2), a significant 17.9% display poor practices, despite having excellent knowledge and a positive attitude. These individuals often resort to stress eating and rarely engage in healthy habits like regular consumption of fruits and vegetables or exercise. Influencing factors range from hunger, taste, food cost, income, food availability, nutrition education, cooking skills, time for meal preparation, culture, family traditions, peer influence, mood, stress, guilt, availability of grocery stores and fast food outlets, work schedules, physical activity levels, to personal health goals [29,30]. The positive correlation between practices and BMI (Table 7) suggests weight loss practices are often adopted post becoming obese. Hence, efforts should be made to support individuals in adopting better weight management practices, especially since poor practice regarding obesity was observed among the overall Douala population [6]. Effective weight management can be achieved through a balanced diet, regular exercise, behavioral changes, regular check-ups, medication adherence, psychological support, and community-based programs [31,32].

The strong correlation between the three components of KAP about obesity (Table 3) highlights the intricate relationship between these elements in health

contexts. It emphasizes the need for comprehensive health education programs that enhance knowledge, nurture positive attitudes, and foster healthy practices. Identifying and addressing barriers to knowledge implementation is crucial [33]. KAP about obesity are influenced by socio-demographic factors and medical history (Table 4). For instance, females showed a better understanding of obesity, possibly due to societal norms, health awareness, or access to health information. Age, education, and employment status also play significant roles in shaping attitudes and practices related to obesity. These findings stress the importance of considering demographic factors in obesity prevention and management strategies [34,35]. Medical history, such as the presence of diabetes or hypertension, can also influence an individual's KAP about obesity. These observations underscore the importance of personalized approaches in designing obesity prevention and management strategies, especially for individuals with chronic conditions like diabetes and hypertension [36,37].

Our research extended beyond KAP related to obesity, encompassing KAP related to diabetes and hypertension among participants. The observed trends (Table 2) showed minor deviations from those recorded for obesity-related KAP. Despite having adequate knowledge and a positive attitude towards diabetes and hypertension, overweight and obese individuals in Douala often fail to adopt preventive or management practices for these comorbidities. This is corroborated by the negative correlation between practices concerning diabetes and hypertension and knowledge about obesity, and knowledge about diabetes and hypertension (Table 3). As indicated in this study (Table 4), patients often become aware of these comorbidities only after they have developed. Participants with diabetes and obesity appear to have superior KAP regarding obesity compared to those without these comorbidities. The influence of socio-demographic factors (Table 4) on KAP is similar to that observed for obesity. These findings underscore the importance of interventions that educate and assist individuals in translating their knowledge and positive attitudes into health-promoting behaviors. This is particularly vital for overweight and obese individuals, as adopting such practices can help prevent the onset of comorbidities, potentially leading to Metabolic Syndrome (MetS).

The second key aspect of this study involved evaluating participants' blood sugar levels, pulse rate, and systolic and diastolic blood pressure, providing a comprehensive understanding of their health status, particularly in relation to obesity, diabetes, and hypertension. Despite being overweight or obese, most participants maintained normal blood sugar levels (Table 5), indicating effective glycaemia management. A small group with high blood sugar was identified as diabetic. Obesity, a significant contributor to type 2

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diabetes, is linked with insulin resistance and can lead to both micro and macrovascular complications [7]. In terms of pulse rate, most readings were within the normal range, but a few participants exhibited high rates (Table 5). Overweight and obesity can influence heart rate, potentially leading to tachycardia. Participants with high pulse rates were often diagnosed as diabetic and/or hypertensive. Tachycardia, diabetes, and hypertension are interconnected, often coexisting and exacerbating each other [38]. Regarding blood pressure, over 50% of participants had high systolic pressure and about 30.8% had high diastolic pressure (Table 5). Obesity, a major risk factor for hypertension, forces the heart to work harder, resulting in increased blood pressure. High blood pressure was more common in participants with diabetes and/or hypertension. Diabetes and hypertension often coexist, sharing risk factors like obesity, unhealthy diet, physical inactivity, and certain genetic factors. Their coexistence can lead to serious complications [38].

The research reveals that obese individuals generally exhibit elevated levels for all clinical parameters, except pulse rate (Table 5). This is supported by the correlation between BMI and these parameters (Table 6), suggesting a pattern where an increase in BMI corresponds to a rise in blood sugar, pulse rate, and blood pressure. Additionally, an increase in any one of these four parameters often aligns with a rise in the others, emphasizing the interconnected nature of these health indicators and the necessity of regular monitoring in managing obesity. Socio-demographic factors such as gender, age, education, and employment status significantly influence these health indicators (Table 4). Therefore, these factors should be considered when assessing health risks and formulating intervention strategies. Regular monitoring and understanding of these parameters can aid in developing effective treatment plans and enable individuals to better manage their health. Effective control of these parameters necessitates improving KAP on obesity, diabetes, and hypertension across the entire population. This study noted negative correlations (Table 7) between the respondents' KAP and certain clinical parameters, suggesting that enhancing KAP could indirectly lead to the control of these parameters in overweight or obese patients. These findings underscore the complex relationship between KAP components and clinical parameters, and the importance of comprehensive education and intervention strategies. By improving people's understanding of these conditions, we can encourage healthier lifestyle choices, enhance self-management, and ultimately, prevent or reduce the incidence of these diseases [39]. Public health initiatives, community outreach programs, and health education can be effective strategies to improve KAP. These efforts can be supplemented with regular health check-

ups and screenings to monitor these clinical parameters and provide early intervention when necessary.

Conclusion

This study analyzes the KAP regarding obesity, diabetes, and hypertension, and clinical parameters among overweight individuals in Douala. It uncovers that, despite possessing sufficient knowledge and a favorable attitude, a significant number of individuals do not implement preventive or management measures for these conditions. Socio-demographic factors and medical history significantly influence these health indicators.

Over half of the participants had high blood pressure, while most had normal glycaemia and pulse rate. This highlights the complex relationship between KAP and clinical parameters, stressing the need for comprehensive education and intervention strategies. Improving KAP could indirectly control clinical parameters in overweight patients. Public health initiatives, community outreach, and health education can enhance KAP, promote healthier lifestyle choices, and reduce disease prevalence.

Ultimately the study underscores the importance of a holistic approach in managing obesity and related conditions. It advocates for strategies that enhance knowledge, foster positive attitudes, and promote healthy practices. Regular monitoring of clinical parameters is crucial. The study's insights can guide healthcare professionals, policy makers, and individuals in managing obesity and associated risks.

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Data Availability

The data used in this study are available from the corresponding authors upon request.

Conflicts of interest

Authors declare no conflict of interest.

Ethics approval

This study was approved by the University of Douala Institutional Ethics Committee (N°2714CEI-Udo/06/2021/M).

Consent to participate

Informed consent was obtained from each participant.

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Appendix

Table 4: KAP Regarding Obesity, Diabetes and Hypertension among Overweight and Obese Individuals from Douala, Based on Socio-Demographic Factors and Medical History

	Knowledge				Attitude			Practices				
	Poor	Good	Excellent	P	Negative	Positive	P	Very poor	Poor	Good	Excellent	P
KAP OBESITY												
Socio-demographic parameters												
Gender												
Male (n = 244)	12 (5.0%)	72 (29.5%)	167 (68.5%)	0.0020	22 (9.0%)	222 (91.0%)	0.0006	4 (1.6%)	35 (14.3%)	124 (50.8%)	81 (33.3%)	0.0010
Female (n = 299)	0 (0.0%)	62 (20.7%)	237 (79.3%)		7 (2.3%)	292 (97.7%)		6 (2.0%)	61 (20.4%)	101 (33.8%)	131 (43.8%)	
Age												
<30 (n = 85)	0 (0.0%)	24 (28.2%)	61 (71.8%)	ns	9 (10.6%)	76 (89.4%)	0.012	2 (2.4%)	23 (27.1%)	32 (37.6%)	28 (32.9%)	0.016
[30-50[(n = 291)	5 (1.7%)	65 (22.3%)	221 (75.9%)		12 (4.1%)	279 (95.9%)		0 (0.0%)	41 (14.1%)	124 (42.6%)	126 (43.3%)	
≥50 (n = 167)	0 (0.0%)	45 (26.9%)	122 (73.1%)		8 (4.7%)	159 (95.3%)		8 (4.7%)	32 (19.2%)	69 (41.3%)	58 (34.8%)	
Education												
Primary studies (n = 18)	0 (0.0%)	10 (55.6%)	8 (44.4%)	0.0048	6 (33.3%)	12 (66.7%)	<0.0001	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	11 (61.1%)	7 (38.9%)	0.026
Secondary studies (n = 269)	5 (1.9%)	60 (22.3%)	204 (75.8%)		7 (2.6%)	262 (97.4%)		5 (1.9%)	62 (23.0%)	100 (37.2%)	102 (37.9%)	
University studies (n = 256)	0 (0.0%)	64 (25.0%)	192 (75.0%)		16 (6.3%)	240 (93.7%)		5 (2.0%)	34 (13.3%)	114 (44.5%)	103 (40.2%)	
Employment												
Working (n = 331)	5 (1.5%)	83 (25.1%)	243 (73.4%)	ns	16 (4.8%)	315 (95.2%)	ns	5 (1.5%)	38 (11.5%)	149 (45.0%)	139 (42.0%)	<0.0001
Not working (n = 141)	0 (0.0%)	31 (22.0%)	110 (78.0%)		10 (7.1%)	131 (92.9%)		4 (2.8%)	44 (31.2%)	48 (34.0%)	45 (32.0%)	
Retirement (n = 71)	0 (0.0%)	20 (28.2%)	51 (71.8%)		3 (4.2%)	68 (95.8%)		1 (1.5%)	14 (19.7%)	28 (39.4%)	28 (39.4%)	
Medical history												
Diabetes												
Yes (n = 78)	5 (6.4%)	23 (29.5%)	50 (64.1%)	<0.0001	5 (6.4%)	73 (93.6%)	ns	4 (5.1%)	22 (28.2%)	29 (37.2%)	23 (29.5%)	0.0035

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No (n = 465)	0 (0.0%)	111 (23.9%)	354 (76.1%)		24 (5.2%)	441 (94.8%)		6 (1.3%)	74 (15.9%)	196 (42.2%)	189 (40.6%)	
Hypertension												
Yes (n = 159)	5 (3.1%)	44 (27.7%)	110 (69.2%)	0.0011	15 (9.4%)	144 (90.6%)	0.0063	8 (5.0%)	36 (22.6%)	72 (45.3%)	43 (27.1%)	<0.0001
No (n = 384)	0 (0.0%)	40 (23.4%)	294 (76.6%)		14 (3.7%)	370 (96.3%)		2 (0.5%)	60 (15.7%)	153 (39.8%)	169 (44.0%)	
KAP DIABETES AND HYPERTENSION												
Socio-demographic parameters												
Gender												
Male (n = 244)	12 (4.9%)	29 (11.9%)	203 (83.2%)	0.0342	11 (4.5%)	233 (95.5%)	0.0078	43 (17.6%)	196 (80.3%)	51 (2.1%)	0 (0.0%)	0.0181
Female (n = 299)	29 (9.7%)	47 (15.7%)	223 (74.6%)		32 (10.7%)	267 (89.3%)		41 (13.7%)	258 (86.3%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	
Age												
<30 (n = 85)	6 (7.1%)	26 (30.6%)	53 (62.3%)	<0.0001	6 (7.1%)	79 (92.9%)	ns	15 (17.6%)	70 (82.4%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	ns
[30-50[(n = 291)	26 (8.9%)	37 (12.8%)	228 (78.3%)		22 (7.5%)	269 (92.5%)		42 (14.4%)	244 (83.9%)	5 (1.7%)	0 (0.0%)	
≥50 (n = 167)	9 (5.4%)	13 (7.8%)	145 (86.8%)		15 (9.0%)	152 (91.0%)		27 (16.2%)	140 (83.8%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	
Education												
Primary studies (n = 18)	1 (7.0%)	9 (48.6%)	8 (44.4%)	0.0061	8 (44.4%)	10 (55.6%)	0.0032	4 (22.2%)	14 (77.8%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0.0042
Secondary studies (n = 269)	22 (8.2%)	29 (10.8%)	218 (81.0%)		25 (9.3%)	244 (90.7%)		29 (10.8%)	240 (89.2%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	
University studies (n = 256)	18 (6.4%)	29 (11.5%)	210 (82.1%)		18 (7.0%)	238 (93.0%)		31 (11.9%)	220 (86.1%)	5 (2.0%)	0 (0.0%)	
Employment												
Working (n = 331)	29 (8.8%)	41 (12.4%)	261 (78.8%)	ns	23 (6.9%)	308 (93.1%)	ns	51 (15.4%)	275 (83.1%)	5 (1.5%)	0 (0.0%)	ns
Not working (n = 141)	5 (3.5%)	28 (19.9%)	108 (76.6%)		10 (7.1%)	131 (92.0%)		22 (15.6%)	119 (84.4%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	
Retirement (n = 71)	7 (9.9%)	7 (9.9%)	57 (80.2%)		10 (14.1%)	61 (85.9%)		12 (16.9%)	59 (83.1%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	
Medical history												
Diabetes												
Yes (n = 78)	8 (10.3%)	4 (5.1%)	66 (84.6%)	0.0399	10 (12.8%)	68 (87.2%)	ns	11 (14.1%)	67 (85.9%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	ns
No (n = 465)	33 (7.1%)	72 (15.4%)	360 (77.5%)		33 (7.1%)	432 (92.9%)		73 (15.7%)	387 (83.2%)	5 (1.1%)	0 (0.0%)	
Hypertension												

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Yes (n = 159)	4 (2.5%)	27 (17.0%)	128 (80.5%)	0.0106	11 (6.9%)	148 (93.1%)	ns	27 (17.0%)	132 (83.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	ns
No (n = 384)	37 (9.6%)	49 (12.8%)	298 (77.6%)		32 (8.3%)	352 (91.7%)		57 (14.8%)	322 (83.9%)	5 (1.3%)	0 (0.0%)	

Note: KAP: Knowledge, attitude, and practices; ns: not significant at P < 0.05

